

Scelionidae [*Telenomus cirphivorus* Liu.], and Carabidae [*Calathus halensis* Schall., *Calosoma maderae chinense* Kirby].

Seasonal migration in eastern China was traced by releasing and recapturing marked moths. Results indicate that the moth is a regular immigrant from the southern provinces to the northeast in early spring. A return migration takes place in late summer or fall.

The maize armyworm *Mythimna loreyi* Duponchel is found in Chekiang, Kiangsu, Kwangtung, Kwangsi, Fukien, Hunan, Hupeh, Szechuan, Kweichow, Kiangsi, Taiwan, and Ginsu Provinces. In Kwangtung, it damages rice in June-July by feeding on the leaves and cutting the spikelets. Parasites of *M. loreyi* include Tachinidae [*Cuphocera varia* Fabricius, *Pseudogonia rufifrons* (Wied.)], Braconidae [*Apanteles* sp.], and Ichneumonidae [*Enicospilus* sp.].

The grain armyworm *Mythimna compta* (Moore) is found in Hupeh, Hunan, Kiangsi, Yunan, Fukien, Chekiang, Kweichow, Kwangtung, and Kwangsi Provinces. In Fukien, it causes significant injury in June-July during its second generation and serious damage in October-November during its fifth generation. In Kwangtung, its infestation on rice is lighter than other species.

The millet armyworm *Mythimna zea* (Duponchel) infests wheat, millet, and rice in Sinkiang Province in the west-northern part of China. It produces two generations a year and the full-grown larva hibernates in the soil. The first generation in June-July causes significant damage.

The nutgrass armyworm *Spodoptera mauritia* Boisduval is found in Kiangsu, Hupeh, Kiangsi, Kwangsi, Kwangtung, Taiwan, and Fukien Provinces. Caterpil-

lars of the 5th generation attack rice severely in Kwangtung in July-August. It often occurs in rice fields that are easily flooded. An outbreak is closely related to water in the fields.

The small nutgrass armyworm *Spodoptera abyssinia* Guenée occurs in Hunan, Fukien, Kwangsi, and Kwangtung Provinces. The caterpillars infest rice seedlings during the second season in June-July in Kwangtung. The duration of the summer generation lasts about 33 days in Guangzhou.

The green nutgrass armyworm *Spodoptera depravata* (Butler) is found in Giling, Shensi, Hupeh, Kiangsi, Szechuan, Chekiang, Kiangsu, Fukien, and Kwangtung Provinces.

The striped nutgrass armyworm *Spodoptera pecten* Guenée occasionally infests rice in Fukien, Kwangtung, and Kwangsi Provinces. ■

Weed hosts of some rice pests in North Western Sierra Leone

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Grasses in the rice fields of associated tidal mangrove swamps of Mawirr and Magbolontor and the mangrove swamp of the Rice Research Station in Rokupr, Kambi District, North Western Sierra Leone, were examined for adults, eggs, larvae, and nymphs of rice insect pests (see table). Insects at immature stages were reared to adults for identification. ■

Distribution of some rice insects on weeds in North Western Sierra Leone.

Insect	Insect stage	Site	Weed host	Rice crop stage
<i>Diopsis thoracica</i> West.	Eggs and adults	Mawirr	<i>Rottboellia exaltata</i> L.f.	Heading
<i>Nephotettix modulatus</i> Melichar	Nymphs	Mawirr	<i>R. exaltata</i>	Heading
			<i>Ischaemum rugosum</i> Salisb.	Heading
<i>Herpetogramma licarsialis</i> Walk.	Larvae	Rokupr mangrove swamp	<i>Paspalum vaginatum</i> Swartz	Vegetative
		Mawirr	<i>I. rugosum</i>	Heading
<i>Epilachna similis</i> Muls.	Nymphs and adults	Mawirr	<i>R. exaltata</i>	Heading
<i>Pteronemobius</i> sp.	Eggs	Mawirr	<i>R. exaltata</i>	Heading
<i>Hydrellia</i> sp.	Feeding lesions	Mange	<i>Pennisetum purpureum</i> Schumach.	Heading

Life span and tungro transmission of viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens*

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The rice tungro virus Collaborative Project investigated the life span and tungro transmission of *Nephotettix virescens*. In two trials in Thailand, 80 adult insects—40 females and 40 males—each for 10 varieties were given 4 days

access on tungro-diseased plants.

Transmission of the tungro virus was lowest in Gampai 30-12-15, Habiganj DW8, and Ambemohar 159, although these varieties were as susceptible to the hopper as TN1, based on life span.

Insect life spans ranged from 1 to 39 days, with an average of 7 days (7.5 for females and 6 for males). The short life spans on Pankhari 203 and Ptb 18 indicated that these varieties were more resistant than the others in the test. ■

Rice insect pests in Vietnam

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The pattern of incidence of insect pests in Vietnam has changed considerably since the introduction of high-yielding rice varieties and accompanying technology in 1968. Several minor insect pests have become major economic factors (see table).

Changes in the economic importance of rice insect pests in Vietnam.

Insect	Economic importance ^a	
	1956-68	1969-81
<i>Cnaphalocrocis medinalis</i> (Guenée)	–	XXX
<i>Tetroda histeroideis</i> Fabricius	–	XX
<i>Baliothrips bififormis</i> (Bagnall)	–	X
<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i> (Stål)	X	XXX
<i>Mythimna unipuncta</i> (Haw.)	XXX	XXX
<i>Orseolia oryzae</i> (Wood-Mason)	XX	XX
<i>Chilo suppressalis</i> (Walker)	XXX	XX
<i>Scirpophaga incertulas</i> (Walker)	XXX	XX
<i>Sesamia inferens</i> (Walker)	XXX	XX
<i>Gryllotalpa africana</i> (P. de B.)	X	X
<i>Sogatella furcifera</i> (Horvath)	X	X
<i>Leptocorisa acuta</i> (Thunberg)	X	X
<i>Nymphula depunctalis</i> (Guenee)	X	X
<i>Chlorops oryzae</i> (Mats.)	X	X
<i>Nephotettix nigropictus</i> (Stål)	X	–
<i>Nephotettix virescens</i> (Distant)	X	–
<i>Scotinophora lurida</i> Burmeister	X	–
<i>Parnara guttata</i> (Bremer & Grey)	XXX	–
<i>Pelopidas mathias</i> (Fabr.)	XXX	–
<i>Spodoptera mauritia</i> (Boisb.)	XXX	–
<i>Dicladisua armigera</i> (Olivier)	XXX	–

^axxx = causing severe damage every year; xx = causing extensive damage in some areas every year; x = causing heavy damage under certain conditions; – = negligible damage.

Nilaparvata lugens, a minor problem during the 1960s, has become increasingly prevalent during the 1970s in sev-

eral rice-growing areas. *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* shows a similar change.

But *Spodoptera mauritia*, *Parnara*

guttata, *Pelopidas mathias*, and *Dicladispa armigera*, defined as major insect pests in the 1960s, are minor pests now.

Incidence of some insects has increased in certain areas of the country during critical times of the growing season. *Chilo suppressalis*, *Scirpophaga incertulas*, and *Sesamia inferens* are problems in the Red River Delta. *C. suppressalis* causes extensive damage in the dry season, *S. incertulas* in the wet season, and *S. inferens* in both seasons.

Mythimna unipuncta causes serious damage during the preharvest stage in the wet season in the northern provinces. *Orseolia oryzae* is more dominant during seedling and tillering stages in the dry season in the central provinces. *Leptocorisa acuta*, *Tetroda histeroideis*, *Scotinophora lurida*, and *Baliothrips bififormis* occasionally cause extensive damage in some locations. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Deep water

Yellow rice borer incidence in deepwater rice in Thailand, 1981

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Rice borer damage was surveyed in 63 deepwater rice fields distributed over the Central Plains of Thailand. The survey from flood inundation to harvest included 24 farmer-named rice varieties, mostly floating types.

The yellow rice borer *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker) comprised more than 95% of the borer population in rice stems dissected. The number of damaged stems increased from 3% at the early elongation stage to 37% at harvest (see figure). An exceptionally high 71% damaged stems at the ripening stage was recorded for 3 fields of Leb Mue Nahng

Average incidence of stems damaged by rice borer, predominantly the yellow rice borer *Scirpophaga incertulas*, in deepwater rice fields. Thailand, 1981.

111 at Prachin Buri.

At an outbreak threshold of 20% damaged stems, 67% of the fields were at outbreak level in the booting and

heading stage and 89% were at harvest. Counts in 35 fields at harvest showed 2.5% whiteheads, a ratio of 1 whitehead to 15 damaged stems. ■